

Type 2 diabetes treatment in Denmark: hospital- vs. GP-monitoring

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: Recent government policy in Denmark has been to push regular monitoring of Type 2 Diabetes patients away from specialized hospital clinics into the general practice settings. This study investigates composition of hospital- and GP-monitored T2D patients, and treatment cost-efficiency implications of moving monitoring into primary care for T2D patients which do not require permanent hospital-based monitoring.

Methods: Using administrative databases of hospitalizations, primary care services, and prescriptions, we algorithmically identified T2D patients, and whether they were hospital- or GP-monitored. Socio-demographics, comorbidities, and annual treatment cost were compared across monitoring settings. Patients with an estimated disease severity believed to make them eligible for both treatment loci were kept. Propensity score matching (PSM) was used to overcome remaining selection bias in the estimation of the impacts on annual healthcare costs of being monitored in hospital. Robustness checks, using distance to diabetes clinic as an instrument for hospital monitoring, were applied.

Results: In 2016, approximately 275000 T2D patients were identified, of which 26000 were identified as being regularly monitored in hospital. Compared with patients who were not hospital monitored, hospital-monitored patients: had higher Charlson Comorbidity Index scores; were younger but with longer histories of diabetes; more likely to be male; had higher levels of education; and were less likely to be immigrants. Of 182000 T2D patients eligible for monitoring at both treatment loci 22000 were hospital monitored. At baseline, hospital-based patients had higher annual costs for medications, outpatient admissions, and non-hospital-based specialist care; general practice costs were lower. After applying PSM, the estimated Average Treatment Effects on the Treated for total costs for moderate-disease hospital-monitored patients was approx. 8500DKK; positively driven by outpatient cost (5400DKK) and prescriptions (5400DKK); and negatively driven general practice (-500DKK) and inpatient costs (-1900DKK). No significant impact on costs for non-hospital-based specialist services were identified, nor for hospitalizations originating as emergency visits. Results of the IV model are awaiting access to distance data but will be available before the conference.

Discussion: This study finds evidence that average hospital-monitored T2D patients in Denmark are in poorer health than GP-monitored patients. However, PSM results suggest that there may be net cost savings to be realized by moving care of some moderate-disease hospital-monitored T2D patients to primary care.